

Funding Trends Research

Preliminary Observations and Findings

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Introduction

Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI) is an initiative dedicated to improving funding and resourcing for open technologies and systems supporting research and scholarship. We do this by shedding light on challenges, conducting research, and working with decision makers to enact change. We employ a research-driven approach to guide strategies and action designed to increase the adoption of and investment in open infrastructure, and also to provide resources and analysis to help funders and budget holders assess, evaluate, and make investment decisions about open infrastructure.

This preliminary report aims to increase our collective understanding of the funding for the open infrastructure ecosystem, a core task to fulfilling our mission. Specifically, we seek to better understand the flow of funding into open infrastructure services. Our intention is to understand not only where funding is going but where funding is lacking to sustain an ecosystem of open services supporting research and scholarly communication. We feel it is crucial to our mission that we understand who's funding whom/what and how much so we may identify neglected areas and untapped opportunities to make funding more reliable and consistent over time. The expectation is that open tools and technologies can be the default and ultimately to contribute towards building a thriving open infrastructure ecosystem.

In this report, we present an initial exploration of funding for open infrastructure services by analysing grant information reported by funders from 2010 to 2020. This report is part of IOI's ongoing effort to understand the funding landscape of open infrastructure services documented in previous blog posts: [project overview](#), [key terms and concepts](#), and [survey of available data sources](#). To be able to more comprehensively analyze and understand the financing and resourcing of open infrastructure service providers in research and scholarship, we used financial ratio analysis to understand the [financial health assessment](#) of nonprofits in this space and identified key patterns in their financial risks, strengths, and resource allocation. In the next pages, we present our preliminary findings and offer recommendations for how this work could be improved with the cooperation of funders and recipients to

better understand the funding trends in this diverse and complicated area of research investment.

Data and Method

Data for this report comes from reported cash grants by funders of open infrastructure services. We explore a broad range of definitions of open infrastructure services and identified providers in the space. From there, we collected information on cash awards received by open infrastructure services providers. We collected information from both providers and funders of open infrastructure services, as well as from other collateral sources. However, we identified several gaps in the available data. For instance, providers might report funders' names but not amounts received. For this reason, in this preliminary report, we only use the data reported by funders. As data quality evolves, we plan to incorporate the data from providers of open infrastructure services into future studies.

Our data collection follows an iterative process composed of five subprocesses:

- defining open infrastructure services
- identifying key sources of data
- collecting data
- analyzing data
- sharing preliminary results with stakeholders in the open infrastructure ecosystem

The iterative research process started in 2021, and this report includes the last data collection round, including data up to late 2021. We collected funding information from the websites of funders and compiled this information in the [Reported funding data for open infrastructure](#) dataset available in Zenodo (Dunks & Hernández Ortiz, 2022).

In terms of method, we conducted an exploratory data analysis using funder-reported cash grants. This exploration has the goal of identifying trends in funding allocation as well as gaps in funding information. Our investigation also aims to craft more questions on resource allocation that can be explored in future studies using financial data and input from stakeholders within the space.

We also acknowledge the limitations of this report around six areas. First, we focused on North American and European providers because of the availability of data¹. Second, most of the available data is incomplete, especially regarding timeframes and total amounts of grants. Third, because some providers manage multiple services, it is often not possible to ascertain which service was funded by a grant to the provider². For this reason, we've decided to include all funding to such providers under the assumption that funds of any sort to the organization support its ability to provide services to users. This means that for some providers, the funding shown for a service may be well above what was actually necessary to provide that service because it covers other services or unrelated projects. Fourth, to gain accuracy on funding information, the analysis focuses on cash grants; we do not include in-kind donations. While this type of nonmonetary support is vitally important to providing services, these are rarely tracked and described with the accuracy necessary to properly quantify their value. Fifth, the analysis uses information on grants that have a disclosed amount and could be verified through funder databases; this means that funders that do not disclose funding amounts were not included in the analysis even if their support for an organization has been publicly disclosed. Sixth, for comparison purposes, all grants have been converted into United States Dollars (USD) equivalent; this means that the amounts may be off given currency fluctuations due to the rough estimations used to convert them from the original currency.

Lastly, there are plenty of other funding management elements that are also important to understand the trends in the open infrastructure ecosystem, but that are not included in this analysis. Additional research in this area would ideally include whether the grants were based on open vs. invited calls, post-award assessments, and how the received grant money was allocated (e.g., share for salaries, management capacity, technology investments). We hope to use this preliminary investigation as the first step in creating a more holistic understanding of the funding landscape and to better understand who's powering open infrastructure.

¹ Our intention in the near future is to expand our research and include information from funders and providers of the global south. In addition, we found scant information on grants for global south providers. For instance, we tried to collect data for SciELO and Redalyc but only found information on government grants. We hope to continue monitoring and collecting data to understand funding for open infrastructure services better.

² Particularly, we are communicating with the Center for Open Science (COS) to better identify the specific allocation of resources to open infrastructure services instead of all the resources received from grants as a means to better understand this phenomenon and develop a reasonable means to account for this in our work.

Findings

We identify clear trends in funding allocation. We summarize these findings in four major takeaways. Our intention is to raise decision makers' awareness off existing funding trends and identify the challenges and opportunities for better allocation of resources.

Wellcome, Arnold, Helmsley, Sloan, and CZI among the Major Funders (2010–2020)

We identified at least 21 funders contributing \$106,108,835.39 USD to open infrastructure services between 2010 and 2020. Donation amounts ranged from \$25.8 million to \$58,000 USD. Alone, Wellcome Trust has provided \$25.8 million in open infrastructure services. Arnold Foundation has also been a critical contributor to organizations in the ecosystem by funding services with around \$23 million dollars. Other major funders are Helmsley Charitable Trust, Sloan Foundation, and Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI), contributing \$12.6, \$10.2, and \$5.7 million USD, respectively. In summary, five funders provided 73% of all funding for open infrastructure services; the remaining 27% of funding was distributed among 16 funders. Figure 1 presents the percentage of funding contributed by each funder, and Table 1 presents the sum of funding granted by each funder.

Figure 1

Percentage of Total Funding Contributed per each Funder for 2010 to 2020

Table 1

Funders of Open Infrastructure Services and Sum of Funding for 2010 to 2020

Funder Name	Sum of Funding
Wellcome Trust	\$ 25,823,982.37
Laura and John Arnold Foundation/ Arnold Ventures	\$ 22,988,094.00
The Leona M. and Harry B. Helmsley Charitable Trust	\$ 12,568,430.00
Alfred P. Sloan Foundation	\$ 10,233,375.00
Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI)	\$ 5,732,307.00
Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS)	\$ 4,780,566.00
National Science Foundation (NSF) U.S. entity	\$ 4,372,094.00
The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation	\$ 3,988,500.00
Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation	\$ 3,630,928.00
John Templeton Foundation	\$ 3,609,856.00
Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation	\$ 2,878,677.00
Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE)	\$ 1,539,934.02
National Institutes of Health (NIH) U.S. entity	\$ 1,422,178.00
Arcadia Fund	\$ 850,000.00
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH)	\$ 618,873.00
John D. and Catherine T. MacArthur Foundation	\$ 460,000.00
Robert Wood Johnson Foundation (RWJF)	\$ 184,450.00
James S. McDonnell Foundation (JSMF)	\$ 167,591.00
The Shuttleworth Foundation ³	\$ 101,000.00
William and Flora Hewlett Foundation	\$ 100,000.00

³ Through the Fellowship Program, the Shuttleworth Foundation provided one year grants to individuals seeking to implement innovative ideas for social change. Some of these included founders and leaders of open infrastructure providers and are included here as funding for these services.

Funder Name	Sum of Funding
The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation	\$ 58,000.00
Grand Total	\$ 106,108,835.39

Funding Cycles are Complex, which Leads to Unpredictability of Funding

We looked deeper at the funding of the top five funders of open infrastructure services. Figure 2 reports this information for the same period (2010 to 2020). We observe that funders report scant information on funding timeframes. For us to have an accurate representation of funding cycles, funders should provide detailed information on the award years and the duration of the grants. Lacking this, we use the award year to document cash grants, though acknowledge these funds were likely made available over several years, not just in the year indicated below. For this reason, there is an apparent concentration of funders and funding in some years. The information gaps help to show the complexity of the funding cycles. Each year, changes in funding also change the mix of actors in the ecosystem. Given the complexity of the funding cycles, providers may face challenges in assessing the financial sustainability of their services.

Figure 2
Funding Amount per Year for the Top 5 Funders Between 2010 and 2020

Funders Have Different Profiles: Funding Allocation and Continuity of Support to Services Differentiate Them

We are also curious to identify funders powering the open infrastructure ecosystem. By powering, we mean key funders investing in open infrastructure by supporting different services and providing funding for more than one year. For such analysis, first, we focus on the ten major funders by the number of open infrastructure services supported from 2010 to 2020. Figure 3 shows the number of open infrastructure services in blue bars and funding amounts in green bars. We only present information on funders that supported more than one service.

We observe two emerging funder profiles. One funder profile is those that have invested in numerous services. Sloan Foundation fits this profile; in the last ten years, they have supported at least ten open infrastructure services with \$10.2 million dollars in cash grants. Another funder profile is those funders allocated funding to fewer services but with higher investments. Wellcome Trust fits this profile; they have given \$25.8 million dollars in two open infrastructure services (eLife and ORCID).

Figure 3
Funders Supporting More than One Open Infrastructure Service by Number of Services and Funding Amount for 2010 to 2020

Limited and Incomplete Data Suggest that Some Open Infrastructure Services Received Most Resources

Continuing with this idea of identifying key funders powering open infrastructure, we also explore those funders providing various grants to open infrastructure services. For this analysis, we focus on funders who reported having provided three or more

grants for the same services. Table 2 presents information on funders, recipients, the number of grants received, and the sum of funding for such grants. We observe that some services have received most of the grants. For instance, the Center for Open Science (COS) has received support from at least three funders through 22 grants. In contrast, other services received the support of fewer funders; this is, for instance, the case of eLife, which received the support of Wellcome Trust through four grants⁴.

Figure 4 presents the number of grants and funding amounts per funder and recipient. The blue bars represent the number of grants, and the green bars the funding amounts. Following the same idea as in the above subsection, we identify two funder profiles: One profile is those funders providing numerous grants to the same services, such as the case of the Arnold Foundation supporting COS with 13 grants totaling \$22.7 million USD. The other profile is those funders providing fewer grants but allocating more funding to specific services. For example, Wellcome Trust granted \$25.8 million USD to eLife in only four grants.

Table 2

Funders Providing Three or More Grants to Open Infrastructure Services Between 2010 and 2020

Funder	Recipient of Grants	No. Grants to Same Services	Sum of Funding
Laura and John Arnold Foundation/ Arnold Ventures	Center for Open Science (COS)	13	\$22,713,328.00
Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS)	Omeka	9	\$1,812,880.00
National Institutes of Health (NIH) U.S. entity	COS	6	\$1,422,178.00
Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE)	Zenodo	4	\$1,539,934.02
Alfred P. Sloan Foundation	Dataverse	4	\$2,812,048.00
Wellcome Trust	eLife	4	\$25,797,509.21

⁴ Please note that grants may be the product of a collaborative effort among several funders. In this first exercise, we tried to divide information by funder and recipient. For this reason, results may be overrepresenting the contributions of funders that co-invested with others.

Funder	Recipient of Grants	No. Grants to Same Services	Sum of Funding
Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI)	Jupyter	3	\$1,749,774.00
The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation	Mukurtu	3	\$1,324,500.00
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH)	Mukurtu	3	\$618,873.00
National Science Foundation (NSF) U.S. entity	COS	3	\$1,936,162.00

Figure 4
Funders Providing Three or More Grants (2010–2020) by Service Provider and Funding Amount

Number of Grants to Same Services and Funding Amounts per Funder (2010-2020)

Takeaways

In this document, we present the preliminary observations and findings from our ongoing effort in understanding funding. For this research, we follow an iterative research process composed of defining open infrastructure services, identifying key sources of data, collecting and analysing data, and sharing preliminary results with stakeholders in the open infrastructure ecosystem. Data for this study comes from the reports made by funders of open infrastructure services. We focus on analysing funding data from 2010 to 2020. Our dataset has numerous caveats including incompleteness of information and its focus on cash grants. Despite these limitations, we believe that a preliminary exploration would be useful to identify data limitations and provide some insights on the allocation of funding for open infrastructure services.

From the analysis on funding data, we observed four major trends:

- Five funders (Wellcome, Arnold, Helmsley, Sloan, and CZI) concentrate 73% of all funding for open infrastructure services; the remaining 27% of funding was distributed among 16 funders.
- By analysing funding per year, we found that funding cycles are complex. In other words, given the scant data on funding allocation per year, it may be difficult for providers of open infrastructure services to have certainty on the funding availability from one year to another.
- Funders have different profiles, this is especially true when we compare them by funding amounts granted and by number of grants to open infrastructure services. On the one hand, we have funders allocating a great deal of funding to handful projects, on the other, we have funders diversifying their support by allocating fewer funding to several open infrastructure services.
- A handful of open infrastructure services attract most resources in the ecosystem. This is the case of services receiving grants from multiple funders.

Moving forward, we will continue to work with funders and providers to continue to grow and improve the information available on [open infrastructure funding](#). If you are interested in contributing funding data from your project and/or funding body, [please get in touch](#).

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